

DEVELOPMENT OF INDIVIDUAL LEARNING STRATEGIES OF FUTURE TEACHERS IN A DIGITAL EDUCATIONAL ENVIRONMENT THROUGH INTEGRATION OF INFORMATION SUPPORT TOOLS

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ABSTRACT

The thesis studies the effectiveness of integrating information support tools in the formation of individual learning strategies of future teachers in a digital educational environment. The research methodology is based on a systematic and competency-based approach and offers a model that combines diagnostic, guiding, resourceful and reflexive-analytical functions. This approach allows future teachers to manage their own personal learning trajectory, use digital tools appropriately, and develop pedagogical decision-making skills. Through integration, resources, educational analytics, and personal observations are combined, which makes the learning process personalized and effective. The results of the study serve to optimize the training of future teachers and sustainably develop their pedagogical competencies.

Introduction

Digital transformation in the education system is manifested as a process that requires not only the introduction of technologies, but also a reinterpretation of the content, tools, and results of the teacher's professional activity. For a future teacher, this situation requires, in addition to the traditional components of methodological training, the systematic formation of such competencies as didactic decision-making in a digital environment, adaptation of teaching based on the digital footprint of students, verification of the reliability of information, compliance with copyright and academic integrity standards. The integration of information support tools serves to create a personalized and reflexive learning process. At the same time, the teacher can evaluate his activities and determine ways to develop them based on the results of educational analytics.

Methodological basis: The research methodology is based on the following main approaches:

1. Systemic approach - considers information support tools as a structural element of the digital educational environment, allowing to identify the connections between their goal, content, means and result components. This approach helps to effectively use resources at each stage of the pedagogical process.

2. Competency approach - focuses on the individual learning actions of the future teacher. Information flows, analytical tools and resources serve to develop these actions, which allows to strengthen personal trajectory management and pedagogical decision-making skills.

Functions of information support

1. Diagnostic function - identifying gaps in the initial training and teaching strategies of the future teacher; this process uses tests, microteaching, case analysis, lesson development expertise and reflective diaries. 2. Guiding function - defining a personal learning trajectory; determining which topics, methods and digital tools need to be used.

3. Resource function - providing reliable and methodologically appropriate content in a digital learning environment; resources are sorted according to the criteria of quality, updating and practical application.

4. Reflective-analytical function - self-assessment, understanding mistakes and planning further strategies; develops the skills of pedagogical interpretation of the results of educational analytics. Developing an Individual Learning Strategy through Integration The integration of information support tools creates the following opportunities:

- Increases the future teacher's ability to manage his own learning path.
- Forms the ability to interpret the results of digital traces and educational analytics in a pedagogical sense.
- Develops reflective learning strategies, which allows for independent decision-making and the use of innovative approaches.
- The purposeful integration of resources and tools ensures harmony between didactic goals and technology.

For example, by analyzing students' completed tasks and test results in real time on digital platforms, the teacher adjusts the learning process, provides additional exercises and individual recommendations. In this way, the teacher's pedagogical decisions become more accurate and reliable.

Conclusion

The integration of information support tools serves as an effective mechanism for the development of individual learning strategies of future teachers. The proposed model combines diagnostic, guiding, resourceful and reflexive-analytical functions, increasing the teacher's personal trajectory management and pedagogical decision-making skills in a digital environment. As a result, the student uses digital tools not only at the level of technical skills, but also as an individual strategy aimed at a didactic goal..

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